

PREPARATION OF ANTIBACTERIALS FROM ORGANO-MERCURIALS. PART II

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Fourteen substituted phenylurea and 12 substituted phenylthiourea derivatives have been prepared. All members of the former and 4 members of the latter group were mercurated. The bactericidal action of the two original groups of compounds and that of the mercurated ureas were studied against B.Coli. They have fairly high activities, especially acetoxymercuri-*p*-chlorophenylurea and diacetoxymercuri- α -naphthylurea, which are active in dilutions of 1: 140,000 and 1: 160,000 respectively. The mercurated phenylthioureas being unstable to heat and light are not useful.

In Part I of this series (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 357) the preparation and properties of a series of organo-mercurials derived from some substituted phenoxyacetic acids and from some phenylglycine derivatives were described. Some of these had quite high bactericidal activities *in vitro*. In the present paper the preparation and bactericidal investigation of a number of substituted phenylureas, phenylthioureas and also of a series of mercurated phenylureas have been examined. The introduction of mercury in the molecule in the form of one or two acetoxy-mercuri groups, has been found to increase many times the bactericidal action in all cases. The mercurated thioureas, however, have been proved to be unstable to moderate heat and to light, and are, besides, sparingly soluble in water. These facts prevented a biological study being made with them.

Most of the phenylureas (except the carboxyphenyl derivatives) are already known and are prepared by the action of either urea or KCNO solution on the hydrochlorides of the aromatic primary amines. The thioureas could be prepared by two available methods using KCNS on the hydrochlorides of the bases, or by the addition of ammonia to the phenyl mustard oils, which were themselves prepared from the ammonium dithiocarbamates of the bases.

The only reference available in the literature of the mercuration of compounds similar to the phenylureas seems to be the work of Shah (this *Journal*, 1938, 18, 149).

The mercuration of the ureas was carried out in the cold or at the ordinary temperature in dilute alcohol or acetic acid solution by mercuric acetate. Dimercurated products were obtained at higher temperatures, especially if an excess of the acetate were present. In the case of β -naphthylurea the di-derivative separated mixed with the mono-derivative, whereas only the mono-derivative was obtained from α -naphthylurea. None of the mercurated products seem to have been described before. The corresponding mercurated thioureas decomposed, as stated above, yielding black HgS slowly, and could not therefore be properly used.

The mercury in the products was estimated by the "Gold crucible method" (cf. Whitmore, "Organic Derivatives of Mercury", p. 355) and the nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method.

The bactericidal action against a 24 hours' culture in nutrient peptone-broth of *B. Coli* was studied by the Rideal-Walker Drop method as in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

The following table gives a summary of the bactericidal data.

TABLE I

Organism: *B. Coli*. Period of incubation = 48 hours at 36°.

Substituent.	Ureas.	Maximum effective dilutions of	
		Thioureas.	Mercurated ureas.
Phenyl	1:300	1:400	1:120,000
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	1:300	1:300	1:100,000
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	1:400	1:300	1:100,000
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	1:400	1:400	1:80,000
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	1:300	1:400	1:140,000
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	1:300	1:400	1:120,000
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	1:500	1:300	1:140,000
β -Naphthyl	1:400	1:500	1:140,000
α -Naphthyl	1:600	1:500	1:160,000
<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl		1:500	---
<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	1:400	1:400	1:19,000
<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	1:500	1:500	1:20,000
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	1:200	..	1:20,000

EXPERIMENTAL

As has already been mentioned, the phenyl-, tolyl-, naphthyl- and *m*-nitrophenyl-ureas were prepared and purified by known methods (Davis and Blanchard, "Organic Syntheses", Vol. 1, p 453; Weith, *Ber.*, 1878, 9, 220) The chlorophenylureas separated at first as oils which solidified on keeping in a refrigerator for several hours; after which they were powdered, filtered and washed with dilute acetic acid before recrystallisation from hot water or hot dilute alcohol.

While phenyl-, tolyl- and *m*-nitrophenyl-ureas gave monomercurated products by mercuration with equimolecular quantity of mercuric acetate in dilute acetic acid at the ordinary temperature, β -naphthylurea gave a mixture of mono- and di-mercurated products. The latter being less soluble separated first and were recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. In case of the α -naphthylurea only the di-derivative was obtained.

The position of the acetoxymercuri group was assumed to be *para* to the urea group in the mono-derivatives.

The carboxyphenylureas were prepared as follows: *m*-(or *p*)-Aminobenzoic acid (13.7g., 1 mol.) was first dissolved in hot water (30 c.c.). To this was added slowly 8.1 g. of KCNO (1 mol.) in water (100 c.c.) and the mixture heated at 100° for 3½ hours. The cooled mixture was filtered and washed with water. The residue was then dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide and precipitated by dilute acetic acid. They were recrystallised from hot water or hot alcohol. In the case of anthranilic acid the mixture was heated at 100° for 4 hours and then evaporated to dryness on a water-

bath. The residue was washed with warm water, dissolved in dilute NaOH and reprecipitated with dilute acetic acid. The yield was poor. The mercury derivative could not be obtained pure.

The urea derivatives were mercurated in the usual way and obtained as white amorphous powders, easily soluble in dilute NaOH and insoluble in organic solvents excepting hot acetic acid.

The phenyl-, tolyl- and chlorophenyl-thioureas were prepared through the corresponding mustard oils (Davis and Blanchard, "Organic Syntheses", Vol. 1, p. 437). The naphthyl derivatives were obtained by the action of ammonium thiocyanate on the hydrochloride of the bases (Declermont, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1877, 1, 79). The carboxyphenyl derivatives, which are new, were prepared in the same way in good yield. On mercuration only the di-mercuri derivatives were obtained with phenyl- and tolylthioureas but mono-derivatives in case of the carboxyphenylthioureas.

Table II gives the names, melting points or decomposition temperatures and the analytical data of the phenylureas and thioureas, and Table III gives the decomposition temperatures and percentage of mercury in the mercuri derivatives.

TABLE II

Compounds.	M.p.	% Nitrogen	
		Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenylurea	294°	15.38	15.5
<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenylurea	265°	15.43	15.5
<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenylurea	Does not melt, softens at 180°, finally solidifies.	15.32	15.5
<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenylthiourea	181°	14.44	14.28
<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenylthiourea	185°	13.98	14.28
<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenylthiourea	194°	13.96	14.28

TABLE III

Compounds.	Decomp. temp	% Mercury	
		Found.	Calc.
Acetoxymercuri-phenylurea	125°	50.9	50.8
" <i>o</i> -tolylurea	200°	48.86	49.09
" <i>m</i> -tolylurea	215°	49.18	49.09
" <i>p</i> -tolylurea	238°	49.83	49.09
" <i>o</i> -chlorophenylurea	158°	46.61	46.7
" <i>m</i> -chlorophenylurea	163°	46.82	46.7
" <i>p</i> -chlorophenylurea	172°	46.59	46.7
" (mono) β -naphthylurea	182°	45.18	45.1
" (di) β -naphthylurea	284°	57.29	57.02
Diacetoxymercuri- α -naphthylurea	210°	57.17	57.02
Acetoxymercuri- <i>m</i> -nitrophenylurea	202°	45.49	45.6
" <i>m</i> -carboxyphenylurea	256°	45.54	45.7
" <i>p</i> -carboxyphenylurea	270°	45.58	45.7
" -phenylthiourea		59.62	59.9
" <i>o</i> -tolylthiourea		58.59	58.72
" <i>m</i> -tolylthiourea		58.62	58.72
" <i>p</i> -tolylthiourea		58.65	58.72

In order to test the stabilities of the mercurated phenylureas, 5 representative members, viz. (1) phenyl, (2) *p*-chlorophenyl, (3) *p*-tolyl, (4) α -naphthyl and (5) β -naphthyl derivatives, were shaken at room temperature (about 35°) with the following reagents: (a) *N*-HCl, (b) *N*-KI, (c) *N*-(NH₄)₂S and (d) a dilute hydrazine sulphate solution containing KOH, for about one hour.

Mixture (d) produced reduction to black mercurous oxide with (3) and (4) most rapidly and less so with (5) and (2); (1) being the least easily attacked. Reagent (a) after one hour liberated ionised mercury very slowly with (2) and (5), the filtrate giving pale yellow colour with H₂S solution, but very indistinctly with others. Reagent (b) liberated small amounts of potassium acetate after one hour, as tested with FeCl₃ added to the filtrate, compound (4) giving the deepest colour. Reagent (c) had very slight effect even after one hour, giving faint yellow colour with (3), (4) and (5) but not with (1) and (2). On the whole the compounds may be regarded as being reasonably stable, except to the action of the powerful reducing agent, hydrazine hydrate.

The mercurated ureas were generally formed in good yield and were stable in air or in light and in hot aqueous and alcoholic solution; the naphthyl derivatives, however, turned slightly grey on long exposure to light. They were not decomposed by dilute NaOH (no liberation of HgO) but were slowly decomposed by continued passage of hydrogen sulphide through their warm solution in dilute acids. The introduction of mercury remarkably increased the activity of the urea derivatives. The *p*-chloro derivative and the β naphthyl derivative (both active in 1:140,000) and the α -naphthyl derivative (active in 1:160,000), appear to be quite satisfactory. They may possibly be used with advantage in paper, glue and leather industries.

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